

The relationship of Human Capital and Economic Growth: A Study in European Union Countries

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Abstract – The study focuses on studying three main predictors of economic growth based on the concept of human capital and current scientific literature, namely: government expenditure on education (% of Gross domestic product (GDP)), the rate of doctoral degree holders (% of population above 25) and public expenditures on research and development (% of GDP). To reach the aim of the paper the latest available data for European countries was used, the results show that two out of three variables are significantly associated with the level of GDP per capita, thus, according to the estimated equation, a 1 % increase in government expenditures on education can predict a 24.1 % increase in GDP per capita; at the same time, a 1 % increase in public spending on research and development can be associated with a 45.7 % increase in GDP per capita. Mentioned results should be used while planning the redistribution of public funds during the period of crisis to minimize the negative consequences and to keep the level of economic development and population welfare at the stable level. The started and ongoing economic crisis caused by the global lockdown and consequently the reduction of the level of employment, the reduction in the volume of output and enlarging pressure on the public funds requires finding an efficient way to distribute public funds between essential sectors of economy in order to maximize the economic and social return.

Keywords: Human Capital, Economic Growth, Social Policy, Research and Development

Introduction

The impact of public social policy through the way of redistribution of government expenditures between essential social-oriented sectors on economic growth is attracting special attention in the period of ongoing economic recession that is seen and predicted worldwide starting from 2020. As known, the outstanding influence of education on economic growth is related to the accumulation of human capital, improvement in labour productivity and is considered as a base of technological development and innovation. Thus, government expenditures on education and research and development (R&D) are essential in recovery and stimulation the economic growth.

In this context, it should be mentioned that developing and underdeveloped countries have not yet reached the appropriate level of population education and have higher rate of illiteracy comparing to developed countries, where this level is quite low. Consequently, the developing and underdeveloped countries are seeking economic growth by investing in education of future generations, but it requires the redistribution of public funds, that can weaken the social and economic system. It should be mentioned that governments of developed countries invest in education and R&D higher shares of their GDP, that makes the gap between developed and underdeveloped countries continuously growing, moreover, in order to reach the pre-crisis level of population welfare underdeveloped and developing countries have to distribute their funds with the highest social and economic return.

Related Work

For the first time, the concept of social welfare was the subject of economic study by Pigou “The Economics of Welfare”, in which the author substantiated the importance of social welfare in the context of economic growth. In addition, the author proved the effectiveness of active participation of the state in the redistribution of national wealth through the collection of taxes and subsidies, which contributes to improving the welfare of the population as a whole (Kumekawa, 2017).

It should be mentioned that actualization of the issue on the impact of the public sector on the country's economy is associated with the need to overcome the negative consequences of economic crises and recession, thus, three waves of development and improvement of the public welfare oriented governmental policy. The first one was seen at the time of the Industrial Revolution, when negative outcomes included: rising unemployment, exacerbation of poverty, deepening social conflicts and crises (Chapman, 2007: 428-440). The second wave began after the World War II, when “social market economy” based on the principles of ordoliberalism was formed in Germany. Additionally, Müller-Armack had identified that the peculiarity of the social market economy is the combination of market freedoms with the principle of social equalization, which is achieved through rational public fiscal policy (Rooks, 2017). Also, Galbraith had advocated active state intervention in the social and economic life of the population in order to overcome the negative consequences of market mechanisms by providing social security to the poor, retraining people who lost their jobs and guaranteeing access to education and technological progress. (Davidson, 2005: 103-113). The third wave started at the end of the twentieth century and is ongoing now, it was caused by the negative consequences of globalization, such as: the relatively free movement of labour, finance and capital that make unpredicted and huge loss in the volume of human, financial and physical capital, which leads to a reduction in public welfare and to a slowdown in economic and technological progress. It should be mentioned that the current global pandemic and the worldwide lockdown, that were seen in most of the countries requires the appropriate and efficient response of the public sector in order to remain the achieved level of development, living standards and minimize the potential negative outcomes of the increased rate of unemployment, reduced volumes of production and consumer demand. Thus, this paper aims to study the potential redistribution of national funds in order to stimulate economic growth through investing in human capital.

The importance of education in economic growth is unquestionable, but the object of investing and the time frame required to get the effect are attracting scientists to evaluate the level of influence of those investments on economic growth.

The impact of investments in education can be seen through the concept of human capital that motivates economic growth via effect of level, which increases the productivity of labour (Romer, 1994: 3-22) and the rate effect, which leads to an improvement of a county's competitiveness due to technical progress and innovations (Horwitz, 2005: 20-22).

The development of scientific approaches should be mentioned in this context. The classical theory supported by Adam Smith, Thomas Malthus, and David Ricardo states that economic growth depends on the labour productivity and other factors but does not count for investments in human capital (Smith & Cannan, 2003). Later, the new theory was introduced in the 80s (Romer, 1994: 3-22), which strengthened the importance of education and innovation in long-term economic growth. Also, it should be mentioned that Benhabib and Spiegel (Benhabib & Spiegel, 1994: 143-173) introduced human capital as a factor of production in the Coob-Douglas type of function, their results proved the impact of human capital through an increase in the internal rate of innovation and the rate of technology diffusion. Moreover, the theory on market value states that investments in research and development, intellectual capital lead to an increase in the market value of companies, that in turn positively affects the overall economic growth (Pelinescu, 2015: 184-190).

The existing empirical studies have proved the positive relationship in level and in first-order difference between expenditures on education and economic growth (De La Fuente & Domenech, 2006), moreover, the positive impact of an increase in the years of schooling on GDP per capital was seen among OECD countries (Bassanini & Scarpetta, 1991: 9-56).

At the same time, Funke and Strulik (Funke & Strulik, 2000: 491-515) using new models of economic growth, namely: Uzawa–Lucas model, which includes human capital accumulation and knowledge spillover as a factor of production and Grossman- Helpman model, which introduced the research and development as a factor of production, that contributes to the technological progress and economic growth. Thus, Funke and Strulik (2000) found that the influence of human capital on economic growth varies based on the level of economic development of a particular country, the impact of human capital accumulation on economic growth is higher in relatively less developed countries comparing to highly developed ones.

The special attention should be paid to the main indicators of the level of human capital and its accumulation. In studies various indicators, such as: the results of tests (PISA and TIMS) (Hanushek & Woessmann, 2009; Hanushek & Kimko, 2000: 1184-1208); individual income (assuming that with an improvement in education the income level increases as well) and the average years of education of the population aged 25 years and over (Serena & Freire, 2001: 585-602); the number of people in research and development in the private sector (Izushi & Huggins, 2004); the share of university graduates among the employed population (Outreville, 1999) are used as a proxy for human capital to study its impact on the economic growth.

However, there are some disadvantages of using the number of years of schooling as an indicator of human capital in analyzing its impact and comparison between countries, as the years of schooling do not cover the whole period of studying and the equal number of years of schooling does not mean the equality of obtained knowledge and skills, thus, cannot be used in this context (Pelinescu, 2015: 184-190). Moreover, the study suggested to analyze the impact of human capital on economic growth separately for groups of countries based on their level of development to reach the homogeneity (Pelinescu, 2015: 184-190).

Currently, there are two main measurement of human capital index. The first method is developed by the World Bank and consists of three pillars: survival (among children over 5 years old), school (quality and quantity of education) and health (adult survival rate and healthy growth among children), overall, the human capital index shows the potential level of human capital that a citizen can obtain by age 18, thus, indicates the impact of present healthcare and education expenditures on the potential human capital of future generations. The second approach is presented by the World Economic Forum and includes four dimensions (capacity, development, deployment and know-how) and five age groups to determine the overall human capital potential of a single country.

In order to reach the aim of the paper and based on the analysis of the existing theoretical background and empirical studies the following indicators of human capital are used: governmental expenditures on education as a % of GDP, doctoral degree holders as a rate of population aged above 25 and public spending on research and development as a % of GDP. It should be mentioned in this context that the recent paper on the impact of public education expenditure on GDP (gross domestic product) per capita using the concept of human capital and endogenous growth model proved the existence of a positive effect of public spending on education on GDP per capita (Ifa & Guetat, 2018: 234-246). This study aims to contribute to the existing literature by studying the impact of additional factors on economic growth, that were not considered before.

Methodology and Data Specification

The aim of the paper is to study three predictors of economic growth (measured as gross domestic product per capita) according to the human capital doctrine, namely: government expenditure on education (% of GDP), the rate of doctoral degree holders (% of population above 25) and public expenditures on research and development (% of GDP). To reach the purpose of the study the mentioned data was obtained from the international data bases. The World Bank's database and UNESCO's database for European Union countries, the analysis was conducted based on the latest available data of 2016. To check if mentioned variables can be identified as predictors of economic growth the regression analysis was implemented. The conceptual model of this research is presented on the figure 1.

The study is based on evaluating the following hypotheses:

The study focuses on studying three main predictors of economic growth based on the concept of human capital and current scientific literature, namely: government expenditure on education (% of Gross domestic product (GDP)), the rate of doctoral degree holders (% of population above 25) and public expenditures on research and development (% of GDP).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

H0: there is no relationship between GDP per capita and government expenditure on education as a % of GDP (GE).

H1: there is a relationship between GDP per capita and government expenditure on education as a % of GDP (GE).

$$\text{Model 1: LN GDP pc} = b_0 + b_1 \times \text{GE} + e; \tag{1}$$

H0: there is no relationship between GDP per capita and the rate of doctoral degree holders as a % of population above 25 years old (Doctoral).

H2: there is a relationship between GDP per capita and the rate of doctoral degree holders as a % of population above 25 years old (Doctoral).

$$\text{Model 2: LN GDP pc} = b_0 + b_1 \times \text{Doctoral} + e; \tag{2}$$

H0: there is no relationship between GDP per capita and the level public expenditures on research and development as a % of GDP (R and D).

H3: there is a relationship between GDP per capita and the level public expenditures on research and development as a % of GDP (R-D).

$$\text{Model 3: LN GDP pc} = b_0 + b_1 \times \text{R and D} + e; \tag{3}$$

Education expenditures are mainly covered by state resources and partially private resources before the economic crisis. European Union countries allocate a significant amount of resources from the state budget in order to meet their education expenditures. The budget is allocated by the European Union (EU) countries to support their education expenditures. It has increased and compared to the previous period. Private resources allocated to education in European Union countries that are limited and remained limited in the following periods. Moreover, it resources provide equal opportunities in education in EU countries. Public deficits in the

EU countries due to the effect of the economic crisis create a contraction pressure on the education budget. Therefore, a reduction is made in education budgets compared to previous years in order to reduce the budget deficits due to the recent economic crises. Although this action has a positive effect on budget deficits, it should be known that this action will have negative effects on education in the future. Restrictions in the budget allocate to education due to the economic crisis created an excuse for the special education system and increased the demand for special education in the budget. Thus, the state begins to restrict the state's control and supervisory authority over education. In order for countries to reach their future strategies, they need to plan the budget allocated to education, education services and education quality independently of budgetary concerns.

Results and Discussions

The study focuses on studying three main predictors of economic growth based on the concept of human capital and current scientific literature, namely: government expenditure on education, the rate of doctoral degree holders (% of population above 25) and public expenditures on research and development (% of GDP). The datas are verified on SPSS 22 and their all information in details are given below respectively.

1- The statistical outcomes of the analyzing Model 1 (1) are the following below:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
LN GDPpc 2016	10.212773575637710	.565007901046020	27
GE 2016	5.0366950	1.23366846	27

Correlations

		LN GDPpc 2016	GE 2016
Pearson Correlation	LN GDPpc 2016	1.000	.526
	GE 2016	.526	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	LN GDPpc 2016	.	.012
	GE 2016	.012	.
N	LN GDPpc 2016	27	27
	GE 2016	27	27

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.526 ^a	.277	.231	.495349959232181	.277	6.117	1	16	.025

- a. Predictors: (Constant), GE 2016
- b. Dependent Variable: LN GDPpc 2016

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	9.000	.504		17.849	.000
GE 2016	.241	.097	.526	2.473	.025

Thus, an existing correlation can be seen between LN GDP per capita and government expenditures on education (% of GDP). The suggested variable (GE) explains 23.1% of variance in LN GDP per capita, at the same time it should be mentioned that model 1 (1) is statistically significant, the significance of the coefficients allows to reject H0, the level of government expenditure on education can be successfully used as a predictor of economic growth (GDP per capita). Finally, Model 1 can be rewritten as:
 $LN\ GDP\ pc = 9 + 0.241 \times G.$

2- Statistical outcomes for Model 2 (2) illustrated as following below:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
LN GDPpc 2016	10.283492249846553	.547654061936374	27
Doctoral 2016	.736	.4573	27

Correlations

		LN GDPpc 2016	Doctoral 2016
Pearson Correlation	LN GDPpc 2016	1.000	.379
	Doctoral 2016	.379	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	LN GDPpc 2016	.	.041
	Doctoral 2016	.041	.
N	LN GDPpc 2016	27	27
	Doctoral 2016	27	27

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.379a	.144	.101	.519274403356105	.144	3.358	1	20	.082

a. Predictors: (Constant), Doctoral 2016

b. Dependent Variable: LN GDPpc 2016

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.949	.213		46.614	.000
	Doctoral 2016	.454	.248	.379	1.833	.082

3- Regression analysis of Model 3 (3) displays all information as given the following below:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
LN GDPpc 2016	10.247244850356363	.633782873545932	27
R and D 2016	1.5430	.89792	27

Correlations

		LN GDPpc 2016	R and D 2016
Pearson Correlation	LN GDPpc 2016	1.000	.648
	R and D 2016	.648	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	LN GDPpc 2016	.	.000

	R and D 2016	.000	.
N	LN GDPpc 2016	27	27
	R and D 2016	27	27

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.648a	.420	.397	.49221719284439 1	.420	18.106	1	25	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), R and D 2016

b. Dependent Variable: LN GDPpc 2016

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.541	.191		49.950	.000
	R and D 2016	.457	.108	.648	4.255	.000

Statistical results show the medium level of correlation between the rate of doctoral holders among population aged above 25 and economic growth (GDP per capita), however, the H0 cannot be rejected as significance level is more than 0.05, thus, the rate of doctoral holders cannot be considered as a good predictor of economic growth (model 2).

The statistical outcomes illustrate the medium level of correlation between public spending on research and development and economic growth (GDP per capita), the suggested model 3 is highly significant (Sig. < 0.01), H0 can be rejected, the mentioned variable explains 39.7 % of variance in GDP per capita and can be considered as a good predictor of economic growth. Accordingly, model 3 can be rewritten as: LN GDP pc = 9.541 + 0.457 x R and D.

Conclusion

This study presented three main predictors of economic growth based on the concept of human capital and current scientific literature, namely: government expenditure on education (% of Gross domestic product

(GDP)), the rate of doctoral degree holders (% of population above 25) and public expenditures on research and development (% of GDP).

The conducted analysis for European Union (EU) countries allowed to check three suggested predictors of economic growth, that are identified in accordance with the human capital doctrine. Thus, 3 models were studied using the regression analysis approach and obtained results can be concluded:

- the percent of GDP spent as government expenditure on education can be considered as a good predictor of economic growth, the model and the variable are statistically significant. The estimated equation indicates that a 1 % increase in government expenditures on education can be associated with a 24.1 % increase in GDP per capita.

- public spending on research and development as a share of GDP can be estimated as a good predictor of economic growth, as suggested model and variable are statistically significant. The obtained coefficients show that a 1 % increase in public spending on research and development can be associated with a 45.7 % increase in GDP per capita;

- the rate of doctoral degree holders among population aged above 25 cannot be considered as a successful predictor of economic growth, as the model is not statistically significant and H0 cannot be rejected.

The obtained results should be taken into consideration while deciding the efficient way to redistribute the public funds between essential sectors of economy, specifically during the period of the current global economic crisis. Thus, in order to maximize the future economic and social return the higher share of GDP should be invested in research and development as it is associated with the 45.7% increase in GDP per capita. Moreover, the technological progress and advances lead to an improvement of labour productivity and to an increase in the potential level of production employing available sources.

In an economic data-based system, it is considered entrepreneurs and new companies in the background of job creation and economic development and growth. The ability of new entrepreneurs and innovative companies in the market take a more competitive position due to intense and effective research and development activities. Research and development activities of the European Union (EU) countries are considered to be quite inadequate when compared to government expenditure on education, the rate of doctoral degree holders, and public expenditures on research and development.

Future studies should focus on finding the ways to overcome the negative consequences of the current economic crisis using the public funds and keeping all socially important sectors of economy at the satisfying level.

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